

Dynamic Multi-level Auto-scaling Rules for Containerized Applications

SALMAN TAHERIZADEH^{1,2} AND VLADO STANKOVSKI^{1*}

¹Faculty of Civil and Geodetic Engineering, University of Ljubljana, Jamova cesta 2,
1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

²Artificial Intelligence Laboratory, Jožef Stefan Institute, Jamova cesta 39, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

*Corresponding author: Vlado.Stankovski@fgg.uni-lj.si

Container-based cloud applications require sophisticated auto-scaling methods in order to operate under different workload conditions. The choice of an auto-scaling method may significantly affect important service quality parameters, such as response time and resource utilization. Current container orchestration systems such as Kubernetes and cloud providers such as Amazon EC2 employ auto-scaling rules with static thresholds and rely mainly on infrastructure-related monitoring data, such as CPU and memory utilization. This paper presents a new dynamic multi-level (DM) auto-scaling method with dynamically changing thresholds, which uses not only infrastructure, but also application-level monitoring data. The new method is compared with seven existing auto-scaling methods in different synthetic and real-world workload scenarios. Based on experimental results, all eight auto-scaling methods are compared according to the response time and the number of instantiated containers. The results show that the proposed DM method has better overall performance under varied amount of workloads than the other auto-scaling methods. Due to satisfactory results, the proposed DM method is implemented in the SWITCH software engineering system for time-critical cloud applications.

Keywords: auto-scaling; dynamic thresholds; multi-level monitoring; container virtualization

Received 1 July 2017; revised 18 February 2018; editorial decision 4 April 2018

Handling editor: Dr Jin-Hee Cho

1. INTRODUCTION

Cloud computing as a pay-per-use on-demand offer has become a preferable solution for providing various types of CPU, memory and network-intensive applications over the Internet. These include finite element analysis [1], video streaming, gaming, early warning systems and various other Internet of Things (IoT) time-critical applications.

Achieving favourable quality under the conditions of dynamically varying workload intensity is essential for such applications in order to make them useful in a business context. Taherizadeh *et al.* [2] studied a range of quality metrics that can be obtained by advanced cloud monitoring systems and can be used to achieve high operational quality. For example, applications' quality can be quantitatively measured by response time and resource utilization aspects.

As the workload becomes more dynamic and varies over time, using the lightweight container-based virtualization can support adaptation improvements on both application performance and resource utilization aspects faster and more efficiently

than using VMs [3]. This work uses container-based virtualization technology, particularly Docker¹ and CoreOS² for the delivery of applications in the cloud. Despite container technologies' potential, capabilities for auto-scaling cloud-based applications [4–11] can still be significantly improved. Inadequate auto-scaling that is unable to address changing workload intensity over time results in either resource under-provisioning—in which case the application suffers from low performance—or resource over-provisioning—in which case the utilization of allocated resources is low. Therefore, adaptation methods are required for fine-grained auto-scaling in response to dynamic fluctuations in workload at runtime.

Many existing auto-scaling mechanisms use rules with fixed thresholds, which are almost exclusively based on infrastructure-level metrics, such as CPU utilization. This includes auto-scaling methods employed by commercial VM-based cloud providers

¹Docker, <https://www.docker.com/>

²CoreOS, <https://coreos.com/>

such as Microsoft Azure³ and Amazon EC2⁴, and open-source container orchestrators such as Kubernetes⁵ and OpenShift Origin.⁶ Although such methods may be useful for some basic types of cloud applications, their performance and resource utilization drops when various CPU, memory and network-intensive time-critical applications need to be used [12].

The hypothesis of the present work is that the use of high-level metrics and dynamically specifying thresholds for auto-scaling rules may provide for more fine-grained reaction to workload fluctuations, and thus it can improve application performance and a higher level of resource utilization. The goal of this paper is, therefore, to develop a new dynamic auto-scaling method that automatically adjusts thresholds depending on the execution environment status observed by advanced multi-level monitoring systems. In this way, multi-level monitoring information that includes both infrastructure and application-specific metrics would help the service providers accomplish satisfactory adaptation mechanisms for the various runtime conditions.

The main contribution of this paper can be summarized as follows: (i) introducing a multi-level monitoring framework to meet the whole spectrum of monitoring requirements for containerized self-adaptive applications, (ii) presenting a method to define rules with dynamic thresholds which may be employed for launching and terminating container instances and (iii) proposing a fine-grained auto-scaling method based on a set of adaptation rules with dynamic thresholds.

A fine-grained auto-scaling approach continuously allocates the optimal amount of resources needed to ensure application performance with neither resource over-provisioning nor under-provisioning. Such an auto-scaling method should be able to satisfy application performance requirements (e.g. response time constraints), while optimizing the resource utilization in terms of the number of container instances, as shown in Fig. 1.

With regard to different workload patterns, it is our aim to evaluate the proposed auto-scaling method relating to its ability to support self-adaptive cloud-based applications with a varied number of requests at runtime. Additionally, it is our aim to compare the new method with seven other auto-scaling methods which are predominantly used in current software engineering practices.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents a review of related work focusing on the auto-scaling of VM and container-based applications. Section 3 describes monitoring requirements for containerized applications. Section 4 presents the architecture of the new adaptation method in detail, which is followed by empirical evaluation in Section 5. Section 6 contains a critical discussion of the proposed approach, while conclusions are presented in Section 7.

FIGURE 1. Fine-grained auto-scaling of a containerized application.

2. RELATED WORK

Cloud applications and systems with auto-scaling properties have been discussed in experience studies and are contained in various commercial solutions. This section presents a review of important auto-scaling methods as summarized in Table 1. The similarities and differences among the presented auto-scaling approaches offer an opportunity for comprehensive conception of the term ‘elasticity’ within cloud-based applications. The proposed new method called dynamic multi-level (DM) auto-scaling is also shown for completeness in the last row of Table 1.

2.1. Experience studies

Al-Sharif *et al.* [4] presented a framework called ACCRS (Autonomic Cloud Computing Resource Scaling) to provision a sufficient number of VMs in order to meet the changing resource needs of a cloud-based application. The proposed adaptation approach uses a set of fixed thresholds for CPU, memory, and bandwidth utilization to evaluate states of resources at runtime. The workload can be identified as a heavy or lightweight if any of these attributes violate the thresholds. Their resource scaling framework applies a single-level monitoring system which measures only infrastructure-level metrics, and hence the service response time or application throughput does not have any role in determining the auto-scaling actions.

Islam *et al.* [5] developed proactive cloud resource management in which linear regression and neural networks have been applied to predict and satisfy future resource demands. The proposed performance prediction model estimates upcoming resource utilization (e.g. an aggregated percentage of CPU usage of all running VM instances) at runtime and is capable of launching additional VMs to maximize application performance. In this approach, only CPU utilization is used to train a prediction model, and their approach does not include

³Microsoft Azure, <https://azure.microsoft.com/>

⁴Amazon EC2, <https://aws.amazon.com/ec2>

⁵Kubernetes, <https://kubernetes.io/>

⁶OpenShift Origin, <https://www.openshift.org/>

TABLE 1. Overview of various auto-scaling approaches for cloud applications.

Paper	Virtualization technology	Infrastructure-level metrics	Application-level metrics	Technique	Adjustment ability
Al-Sharif <i>et al.</i> [4]	VM	CPU, memory and bandwidth	Nothing	Rule-based	Static
Islam <i>et al.</i> [5]	VM	CPU	Response time	Linear regression and neural networks	Static
Jamshidi <i>et al.</i> [6]	VM	CPU, memory, etc	Response time and application throughput	Reinforcement learning (Q-Learning)	Dynamic
Arabnejad <i>et al.</i> [7]	VM	Nothing	Response time and application throughput	Fuzzy logic control and reinforcement learning	Dynamic
Tsoumakos <i>et al.</i> [8]	VM	CPU, memory, bandwidth, etc	Response time and application throughput	Reinforcement learning (Q-Learning)	Static
Gandhi <i>et al.</i> [9]	VM	CPU	Response time and application throughput	Queueing model and Kalman filtering	Dynamic
Baresi <i>et al.</i> [10]	Container	CPU and memory	Response time and application throughput	Control theory	Dynamic
Horizontal Pod Auto-scaling (HPA) used by Kubernetes	Container	CPU	Nothing	Rule-based	Static
Target Tracking Scaling (TTS) and Step Scaling (SS) used by Amazon	VM and container	CPU and bandwidth	Application throughput	Rule-based	Static
THRESHOLD (THRES) [11]	VM and container	CPU	Nothing	Rule-based	Static
Multiple Policies (MP) used by Google	VM	CPU	Application throughput	Rule-based	Static
DM	Container	CPU, memory and bandwidth	Response time and application throughput	Rule-based	Dynamic

other types of resources, e.g. memory. The authors propose using a 12-minute prediction interval, because the setup time of VM instances in general is around 5–15 minutes. This low rate of prediction is not suitable for continuously changing workloads. Moreover, in such proactive methods [13–16], for each workload change, it takes too long to converge towards a stable driven performance model, and thus the application may provide poor quality of service (QoS) to the users during the first stages of the learning period.

Jamshidi *et al.* [6] presented a self-learning adaptation technique called FQL4KE to perform scaling actions in terms of increment or decrement in the number of VMs. FQL4KE applies a fuzzy control method based on a reinforcement learning algorithm. However, in some real-world environments, the number of situations is enormous, and therefore the reinforcement learning procedure may take too long to converge for any new change in the execution environment. Therefore, using reinforcement learning may become impractical due to the time constraints imposed by time-critical applications such as early warning systems.

Arabnejad *et al.* [7] proposed a fuzzy auto-scaling controller which can be combined with two reinforcement learning approaches: (i) fuzzy SARSA learning (FSL) and (ii) fuzzy Q-learning (FQL). In this work, the monitoring system collects required metrics such as response time, application

throughput and the number of VMs in order to feed the auto-scaling controller. The auto-scaling controller automatically scales the number of VMs for dynamic resource allocations to react to workload fluctuations. It should be noted that the proposed architecture is usable only for a specific kind of virtualization platform called OpenStack. Moreover, the controller has to select scaling actions among a limited number of possible operations. That means if a drastic increase suddenly appears in the workload intensity, the proposed auto-scaling system is able to add just one or two VM instances that perhaps cannot provide enough resources to maintain an acceptable QoS.

Tsoumakos *et al.* [8] introduced a resource provisioning mechanism called TIRAMOLA to identify the number of VMs needed to satisfy user-defined objectives for a NoSQL database cluster. The proposed approach combines Markov decision process (MDP) with Q-learning as a reinforcement learning technique. It continuously decides the most advantageous state which can be reached at runtime, and hence identifies available actions in each state that can either add or remove NoSQL nodes, or do nothing. The rationale of TIRAMOLA is acting in a predictable manner when the regular workload pattern can be identified. Therefore, previously unseen workloads are the main barrier to quick adaptation of the entire system to address the performance objective of

interactive services. Moreover, TIRAMOLA is limited to the elasticity of a certain type of application like NoSQL databases. Besides this, the monitoring part should collect client-side statistics in addition to server-side metrics (e.g. CPU, memory and bandwidth, query throughput, etc.). To this end, clients need to be modified so that each one can report its own statistics, which is not a feasible solution for many use cases.

Gandhi *et al.* [9] presented a model-driven auto-scaler called dependable compute cloud (DC2) which proactively tends to ensure application performance to meet user-specified requirements. The proposed approach applies a combination of a queuing model and the Kalman filter technique to produce estimations of the average service time at runtime. The functionality of DC2 is focused on preventing resource under-utilization, and hence it may cause an over-provisioning issue during execution time. Furthermore, the Kalman filter process is iteratively continued at every 10-s monitoring interval, it needs some time (e.g. few minutes) to calibrate the driven model based on the monitoring data for every new state. Accordingly, the challenge in this regard is that the accuracy of the proposed auto-scaling approach may decrease for special workload patterns such as a new, drastically changing scenario over time.

Baresi *et al.* [10] presented an auto-scaling technique that uses an adaptive discrete-time feedback controller to enable a containerized application to dynamically scale resources, both horizontally and vertically. Horizontal scaling means the addition or removal of container instances, while vertical scaling represents expanding or shrinking the amount of resources allocated to a running container. In this work, a component called ECoWare agent should be deployed in each VM. An ECoWare agent is responsible for the collection of container-specific monitoring data, such as containers' utilization of CPU, memory, and so on. This component is also in charge of launching or terminating a container in the VM, or changing the resources allocated to a container.

2.2. Production rule-based solutions

Currently, many commercial cloud providers (e.g. Amazon EC2 and Google Cloud Platform), as well as container management systems (e.g. Kubernetes), provide static rule-based auto-scaling approaches which are not flexible enough to adjust themselves to the runtime status of the execution environment. In this subsection, we explain some important rule-based auto-scaling solutions for the purpose of comparison to our proposed DM method. These solutions have been chosen for comparison to our method since they are also rule-based and considered as advanced auto-scaling approaches, and which are used in production systems.

Our goal is to evaluate the proposed DM method through a set of empirical experiments which are presented in Section 5.

FIGURE 2. Important quality properties of cloud-based applications and associated metrics.

Figure 2 complements Fig. 1, and presents two important quality properties which are analysed by the study and lead to the definition of a fine-grained auto-scaling approach.

Generally, a typical practice in current commercial services is to use fixed, single-level scaling rules. For example, it is possible to specify a CPU-based auto-scaling policy that more VMs/containers should be launched if the average CPU utilization is over a fixed threshold such as 80%; while some VMs/containers may be terminated if the average CPU utilization is less than 80%. These settings cannot be very useful for special workload patterns such as drastically changing scenarios. Moreover, they lead to a stable system at 80% resource utilization, which means 20% of resources are wasted, which is not desirable. One of the main open challenges and significant technical issues in proposing an auto-scaling technique is to decide to what extent the adaptation approach should be self-adjustable to changes in the execution environment.

In our proposed auto-scaling method, both infrastructure-level metrics (CPU, memory, etc.) and application-specific metrics (e.g. response time and application throughput) are the factors that dynamically influence the adjustable, auto-scaling rules. Our proposed method is dynamic because it uses self-adaptive rules which are employed for launching and terminating container instances. These rules are adjusted according to the workload intensity at runtime. It means, in our approach, conditions when containers are initiated or terminated can be different and do not need to be predefined.

In the following, we proceed with an analysis of existing auto-scaling methods which are widely used and serve as means for comparison with the proposed DM method.

2.2.1. Kubernetes—horizontal pod auto-scaling

Kubernetes is a lightweight container management system able to orchestrate containers and automatically provide horizontal scalability of applications. In Kubernetes, a pod is a group of one, or a small number of containers which are tightly coupled together with a shared IP address and port space. One pod simply represents a single instance of an application that can be replicated, if more instances are needed to process the growing workload. In Kubernetes, the horizontal pod auto-scaling (HPA) approach [17] is a control

loop algorithm principally based on CPU utilization; no matter how workload intensity or application performance is behaving. HPA (shown in Algorithm 1) is able to increase or decrease the number of pods to maintain an average CPU utilization across all pods close to a desired value, e.g. $\text{Target}_{\text{cpu}} = 80\%$.

A `SUM_Cluster` is the grouping function used to calculate the total sum of the cluster. The period of the Kubernetes auto-scaler is 30 s by default, which also can be changed. At each iteration, Kubernetes' controller increases or decreases the number of pods according to *NoP* as the output of the HPA algorithm.

2.2.2. AWS—target tracking scaling

The Amazon EC2 AWS platform offers a target tracking scaling (TTS) [18] approach, which is able to provide dynamic adjustments based on a target value for a specific metric. This approach applies single-level auto-scaling rules to consider either an infrastructure-level metric (e.g. average CPU utilization) or an application-level parameter (e.g. application throughput per instance). To this end, a predefined target value must be set for a metric considered in the auto-scaling rule. Moreover, the minimum and maximum number of instances in the cluster should be specified. TTS adds or removes application instances as required to keep the metric at, or close to, the specified target value.

The default configuration in AWS is capable of scaling based upon a metric with a 5-minute frequency. This frequency can be changed to 1 minute—which is known as detailed auto-scaling option. TTS is able to increase the cluster capacity when the specified metric is above the target value, or decrease the cluster size when the specified metric is below the target value for a specified consecutive periods e.g. even one interval. For a large cluster, the workload is spread over a large number of instances. Adding a new instance or removing a running instance causes less of a gap between the

target value and the actual metric data points. In contrast, for a small cluster, adding or removing an instance may cause a big gap between the target value and the actual metric data points. Therefore, in addition to keeping the metric close to the target value, TTS should also adjust itself to minimize rapid fluctuations in the capacity of the cluster.

For example, a rule specified as 'TTS1 (CPU, 80%, ± 1)' can be executed to keep the average CPU utilization of the cluster at 80% by adding or removing one instance per scaling action. Moreover, the rule 'TTS' can also be used to adjust the number of instances by a percentage. For instance, a rule named 'TTS2 (CPU, 80%, $\pm 20\%$)' adds 20% more instances or removes 20% fewer instances, if the conditions are satisfied. For example, if four instances are currently running in the cluster, and the average CPU utilization goes higher than 80% during the last minute, TTS2 determines that 0.8 instance (that is 20% of four instances) should be added. In this case, TTS rounds up 0.8 and adds one instance. Or, if in a certain condition, TTS2 decides to remove 1.5 instances, TTS can round down and stop only one instance.

2.2.3. AWS—step scaling

The step scaling (SS) [19] auto-scaling approach can also be applied in AWS. For instance, if the average CPU utilization needs to be below 80%, it is possible to define different scaling steps. Figure 3a shows the first part of an AWS auto-scaling example called 'SS1' to expand the capacity of the cluster, while the workload is increasing. In this example, one instance will be added for a modest breach (from 80% to 85%), two more instances will be instantiated for somewhat bigger breaches (from 85% to 95%), and four instances for CPU utilization that exceeds 95%. The ranges of step adjustments should not overlap or even have a gap. In this example, SS1 periodically calculates the 1-minute aggregated value of the average CPU utilization from all instances. Then, if this value exceeds 80%, SS1 compares it against the upper and lower bounds specified by various step adjustments to decide which action to be performed.

Algorithm 1 Kubernetes HPA algorithm.

Inputs:

$\text{Target}_{\text{cpu}}$: Targeted per-pod CPU resource usage

CLTP : Control Loop Time Period in seconds, e.g. 30 seconds

Outputs:

NoP : Number of pods to be running

```
do{
  Cluster = [Pod1, ..., PodN];
  SumCpu = SUM_Cluster(cpu_usage_of_pod1, ...,
    cpu_usage_of_podN);
  NoP =  $\left\lceil \frac{\text{SumCPU}}{\text{Target}_{\text{cpu}}} \right\rceil$ 
  wait(CLTP);
} while(true);
```

(a)

Take the action:	Instances	When
Add 1 instances	1	when 80 <= CPUUtilization < 85
Add 2 instances	2	when 85 <= CPUUtilization < 95
Add 4 instances	4	when 95 <= CPUUtilization < +infinity

(b)

Take the action:	Instances	When
Remove 1 instances	1	when 50 >= CPUUtilization > 40
Remove 2 instances	2	when 40 >= CPUUtilization > 30
Remove 4 instances	4	when 30 >= CPUUtilization > -infinity

FIGURE 3. An AWS auto-scaling example named SS1.

FIGURE 4. An AWS auto-scaling example named SS2.

Similarly, it is possible to define different steps to decrease the number of instances running in the cluster. As an example, Fig. 3b shows three steps to remove unnecessary instances when the average CPU utilization falls below 50%.

In AWS, step scaling policies can be also defined on a percentage basis. That means to handle a growing workload at runtime, SS is able to increase the number of instances by the percentage of cluster size. Figure 4a shows the first part of an AWS auto-scaling example called ‘SS2’ that includes two-step adjustments to increase the number of instances in the cluster by 20% and 30% of the cluster size at the respective steps. If the resulting value is not an integer, SS2 rounds this value. In this case, values greater than 1 are rounded down. Values between 0 and 1 are rounded to 1. For example, if the current number of instances in the cluster is four, adding 30% of the cluster will result in the deployment of one more instance. As such, 20% of four instances is 1.2 instances, which is rounded down to 1 instance.

It is also possible to define a similar set of policies to decrease the number of instances deployed in the cluster. In this way, SS2 is capable of decreasing the current capacity of the cluster by the specified percentage at different step adjustments. Figure 4b shows a two-step auto-scaling to handle a decreasing workload at runtime, and hence to reduce the number of instances in the cluster by 20% and 30% of the cluster size. The resulting values between 0 and -1 are rounded to -1 . Moreover, the resulting values less than -1 are rounded up. For example, -3.78 is rounded to -3 .

2.2.4. THRESHOLD

THRES (Metric, UP%, DOWN%) [11] is a static single-level auto-scaling method which horizontally adds a container instance if an aggregated metric (e.g. average CPU or memory usage of the cluster) reaches the predefined UP% threshold, and removes a container instance when it falls below the predetermined DOWN% threshold for a default number of successive intervals, e.g. two intervals. ‘THRES1 (CPU, 80%, 50%)’ is an example for such a static single-level auto-scaling method.

The ‘THRES2 (CPU, 80%, 50%, RT, 190 ms)’ method also can be defined as an example for a static multi-level

provisioning approach that is also able to consider the average response time (RT). To add a new container instance, both the average resource utilization and response time thresholds (in this use case, 80% and 190 ms, respectively) should be reached for two consecutive intervals. To remove a container from the cluster, the average CPU usage of the cluster should be less than 50% during the last two periods.

2.2.5. Google—Multiple Policies

The Google Cloud Platform supports an auto-scaling mechanism called ‘MP’ to use multiple auto-scaling policies individually at different levels [20]. For example, the MP auto-scaler is able to consider two policies. One policy can be based upon average CPU utilization of the cluster as an infrastructure-level parameter. Another policy can be based on application throughput of the load-balancer (ATLB) as an application-level metric. In other words, each policy is a single-level rule that is defined and based on only one metric. MP calculates the number of necessary instances recommended by each policy, and then picks the policy that leaves the largest number of instances in the cluster. This feature conservatively ensures that the cluster always has enough capacity to handle the workload.

In this way, a target value should be defined for each metric. For example, ‘MP (CPU = 80%, ATLB = 80%)’ is a two-policy method which continuously collects the average CPU utilization of the cluster, as well as the load-balancing serving capacity. In this example, setting a 0.8 target usage tells the MP auto-scaler to maintain an average CPU utilization of 80% in the cluster. Moreover, MP will scale the cluster to maintain 80% of the load-balancing serving capacity. For instance, if the maximum load-balancing serving capacity is defined as 100 RPS (requests per second) per instance, MP will add or remove instances from the cluster to maintain 80% of the serving capacity, or 80 RPS per instance.

3. MONITORING CONTAINERIZED APPLICATIONS

In comparison to traditional monitoring approaches for data-centres, an advanced cloud monitoring system should be able to monitor various metrics at different levels, including container and application-level metrics, instead of only VM-level metrics [21–24]. When designing a new auto-scaling approach, our aim is to rely on such advanced multi-level monitoring systems as described in the following subsections.

3.1. Container-level monitoring

If the system applies container-based virtualization instead of VMs to use a lightweight mechanism for deploying and scaling services in the cloud, container-level monitoring becomes compulsory. A container-level monitoring system is able to

TABLE 2. Overview of container-level monitoring tools.

Tool	Open Source	License	Scalability	Alerting	TSDB	GUI
cAdvisor	Yes	Apache 2	No	No	No	Yes
cAdvisorIG ^a	Yes	Mixed	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Prometheus	Yes	Apache 2	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
DUCP ^b	Yes	Commercial	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Scout	Yes	Commercial	No	Yes	Yes	Yes

^aUsing three tools together: cAdvisor (Apache 2) + InfluxDB (MIT) + Grafana (Apache 2).

^bDocker Universal Control Plane (DUCP), <https://docs.docker.com/ucp/>

monitor containers and display runtime value of key attributes including CPU, memory, and network traffic usage of each container instances. As listed in Table 2, there are different tools offered specifically for the purpose of monitoring containers and expose value of characteristics for a given container at runtime.

cAdvisor⁷ is a system that measures, processes, aggregates and shows monitoring data obtained from running containers. This monitoring data can be applied as an awareness of the performance features and resource usage of containers over time. cAdvisor only displays monitoring information measured during the last 60 s. However, it is capable of storing the data in an external Time Series Database (TSDB) such as InfluxDB⁸ which supports long-term storage and analysis. Besides that, Grafana⁹ is a Web interface to visualize large-scale monitoring data. Using InfluxDB and Grafana on top of the cAdvisor monitoring system could significantly improve visualizing the monitored metrics in understandable charts for different time periods.

Prometheus¹⁰ is a monitoring tool which includes a TSDB. It is able to gather monitoring metrics at different intervals, show the measurements, investigate rule expressions, and trigger alerts when the system commences to experience abnormal situation. However cAdvisor is considered as the easier monitoring system to be used in comparison to Prometheus, it has restrictions with alert management. It should be noted that both may not be able to appropriately offer turnkey scalability to handle large number of containers.

DUCP is a commercial solution to monitor, deploy and manage distributed applications using Docker. Web-based user interface and high scalability are the notable characteristics of this container management solution.

Scout¹¹ is also a container monitoring system which has a Web interface management console, and is capable of storing measured values taken during at most 30 days. This monitoring solution supports alerting based on predetermined thresholds.

3.2. Application-level monitoring

Application-level monitoring, which is an open research challenge yet, measures parameters that present information about the situation of an application and its performance; such as response time or application throughput. Table 3 shows a list of cloud monitoring systems which are able to measure application-specific metrics.

Zenoss [25] is an agent-less monitoring platform based on the SNMP protocol. This tool has an open architecture to help consumers customize it based on their monitoring requirements. However, it has a limited open-source version and the full version for monitoring requires payment, so its applicability in research is undermined.

Ganglia [26] is a scalable monitoring system for high-performance computing environments such as clusters and grids. This tool is generally designed to collect infrastructure-related monitoring data about machines in clusters and display this information as a series of graphs in a web-based interface. It is not suitable for bulk data transfer due to the lack of congestion avoidance and windowed flow control in Ganglia.

Zabbix [27] which is an agent-based monitoring solution supports an automated alerting ability to trigger if a predetermined condition happens. Zabbix is mainly implemented to monitor network services and network parameters. As a disadvantage to be considered, the auto-discovery characteristic of this monitoring system can be inefficient [28]. For example for Zabbix, sometimes it may take almost five minutes to discover that a host is no longer running in the environment. This restriction in time may be a serious issue for any time-critical self-adaptation scenario.

Lattice [29], as a non-intrusive monitoring system, is mainly implemented for monitoring highly dynamic cloud-based environments, consisting of a large number of resources. The functionalities of this monitoring system are the abilities for the distribution and collection of monitoring data via either UDP protocol or multicast addresses. Therefore, the Lattice platform is not meant for automated alerting, visualization and evaluation [30].

JCatascopia [31] is a scalable monitoring platform which is capable of monitoring federated clouds. This open-source monitoring tool is designed for server/agent architecture. Monitoring Agents are able to measure whether infrastructure-specific

⁷cAdvisor, <https://github.com/google/cadvisor>

⁸InfluxDB, <https://influxdata.com/time-series-platform/influxdb/>

⁹Grafana, <http://grafana.org/>

¹⁰Prometheus, <https://prometheus.io/>

¹¹Scout, <https://scoutapp.com/>

TABLE 3. Overview of application-level monitoring tools.

Tool	Open Source	License	Scalability	Alerting	TSDB	GUI
Zenoss	Yes	GPL	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Ganglia	Yes	BSD	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Zabbix	Yes	GPL	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Lattice	Yes	Apache 2	Yes	No	No	No
JCatascopia	Yes	Apache 2	Yes	No	Yes	Yes

parameters or application-level metrics, and then they send the monitoring data to a central entity called a Monitoring Server.

3.3. The SWITCH monitoring system

The SWITCH project¹² provides a software engineering platform for time-critical cloud applications [12]. In order to develop a monitoring system for SWITCH, JCatascopia has been chosen as the baseline technology and was extended to be able to measure container-level metrics. Each container consists of two parts: an application instance and a Monitoring Agent. Monitoring Agents are the actual components that collect individual metrics' values. Since JCatascopia is written in Java, each container which includes a Monitoring Agent requires some packages and a certain amount of memory for a Java virtual machine (JVM) even if the monitored application running alongside the Monitoring Agent in the container is not programmed in Java. Therefore, Monitoring Agents in the SWITCH project have been implemented through the StatsD protocol¹³ available for many programming languages such as C/C++ and Python. Accordingly in the SWITCH platform, a running container includes: (i) a service as application instance and (ii) a StatsD client as a Monitoring Agent.

The functioning of the SWITCH monitoring system is illustrated in Fig. 5.

In Fig. 5, two different container images (📦 and 📦) have been pulled from a local registry, and each one provides a different scalable service, for example Service X and Service Y. Therefore, there are two different service clusters in this figure. Starting a new container instance of a given service means that the service scales up, and stopping it means that it scales down. Once a new container is instantiated, it is allocated to a logical cluster. The SWITCH monitoring system keeps track of these logical clusters for every running service. For example, Fig. 5 shows that Cluster 1 hosts three instances of Service X and Cluster 2 hosts two instances of Service Y.

The monitoring data streams coming from Monitoring Agents to the Monitoring Server via the StatsD protocol are stored in a Cassandra TSDB for the storage of series of time-ordered data points. The SWITCH web-based interactive development environment (IDE) allows all external entities to access the

FIGURE 5. The SWITCH monitoring system.

monitoring information stored in the TSDB in a unified way, via prepared REST-based web services, APIs and diagrams.

For the SWITCH platform, a container image (📦) as shown in Fig. 5) has been built to include the following three entities: (i) a StatsD server as Monitoring Server, (ii) TSDB and (iii) the SWITCH web-based IDE. This container image is open-source and publically released on Docker Hub [32]. It should be noted that it is also possible to have individual container images for every one of these three entities. The SWITCH monitoring system is freely available to researchers at GitHub [33] under an Apache 2 license.

¹²The SWITCH project, <http://www.switchproject.eu/>

¹³The StatsD protocol, <https://github.com/etsy/statsd/wiki>

A Docker registry which can be installed locally is used to store Docker images. Using a local registry makes it faster to pull container images and run container instances of services across cluster nodes. A local Docker registry significantly reduces deployment latency and network overhead when running containers across the spread of host machines in a region. Moreover, it may be possible to design deployment strategies that make use of cached container images, thus, further improving deployment time.

4. METHOD AND ARCHITECTURE

This study introduces a DM auto-scaling method which is included together with the SWITCH monitoring system in a functional architecture (shown in Fig. 6) for adaptive containerized applications.

In our work, we consider that each host in a cluster is able to include at most one container instance per service, while one host can belong to different clusters at the same time. That means more than one container instance can be deployed on one host, but nevertheless they should provide different services. This situation is a realistic case of an operational environment where different types of services should be scaled. When a specific service is instantiated at the host, it exposes its interfaces at specific port numbers, which must not clash with the port numbers of other instantiated services. Then, it makes sense to provide an internal, so-called vertical elasticity mechanism for the allocation of CPU and memory resources to different services within the same host machine, but, it would

make no sense to instantiate additional instances of the same service on the same host machine.

Generally, if two or more containers run on a host machine, by default all containers will get the same proportion of CPU cycles. In this situation, if tasks in one container are idle, other containers are able to use the leftover CPU cycles. Moreover, it is possible to modify identical proportions assigned to running containers by using a relative weighting mechanism. In such a manner, when all containers running on a host machine attempt to use 100% of the CPU time, the relative weights give each container access to a defined proportion of the host machine’s CPU cycles (since CPU cycles are limited).

When enough CPU cycles are available, all containers running on a host machine use as much CPU as they need regardless of the assigned weights. However, there is no guarantee that each container will have a specific amount of CPU time at runtime. Because the actual amount of CPU cycles allocated to each container instance will vary depending on the number of containers running on the same host machine and the relative CPU-share settings assigned to containers. To ensure that no container can starve out other containers on a single host machine, if a running container includes a CPU-bound service, other containers that will be deployed on that machine should not be identified as computationally intensive services. This principle has been adopted also for memory-intensive applications. In this work, all containers have the same weight to gain access to the CPU cycles and the same limit at the use of memory. This makes it an appropriate case of so-called horizontal scaling.

FIGURE 6. Auto-scaling architecture for adaptive container-based applications.

The proposed architecture includes the following components: Load-Balancer, Monitoring Agent, Monitoring Server, TSDB, Alarm-Trigger and Self-Adapter. These are explained in detail in the following subsections.

4.1. Load-Balancer

The Load-Balancer (e.g. HAProxy) provides high-availability support for containerized applications by spreading requests across multiple container instances.

4.2. Monitoring Agent, Monitoring Server, TSDB and the SWITCH Web-based IDE

The monitoring system is able to measure both container-level metrics (e.g. CPU and memory usage of containers) and application-level parameters (e.g. average response time and throughput of the application). Therefore, two types of Monitoring Agents which measure container-level and application-level metrics are included in the architecture.

The application-level Monitoring Agent is in charge of monitoring the Load-Balancer. Application-level metrics which are applied in the context of the proposed auto-scaling method are *AvgRT* (average response time to reply to a user's request), *AT* (application throughput which means the average number of requests per second processed by one container instance), and *cont* (number of container instances behind the Load-Balancer).

The distributed nature of our developed agent-based monitoring system supports a fully interoperable, lightweight architecture which quenches the runtime overhead of the whole system to a number of Monitoring Agents. A Monitoring Agent which is running alongside the application in a container collects individual metrics and aggregates the measured values to be transmitted to the Monitoring Server. The Monitoring Server is a component that receives measured metrics from the Monitoring Agents. This monitoring system is able to store measured values in the Apache Cassandra server as TSDB.

When a container is launched, the Monitoring Agent will automatically send the Monitoring Server a message to register itself as a new metric stream, and then it will start collecting metrics and continuously forward the measured values to the Monitoring Server.

The SWITCH web-based IDE is also used to set primitive thresholds needed for adaptation policies. It is also a key tool used by software engineers to analyse events in a dynamically changing cloud environment.

4.3. Alarm-Trigger

The Alarm-Trigger is a rule-based component which checks the incoming monitoring data and notifies the Self-Adapter when the system is going to experience abnormal behaviour. The Alarm-Trigger continuously processes two functions. One function named checking for container instantiation

(*CFCI*) has been defined in the Alarm-Trigger to investigate if it is needed to start new container instances. Moreover, another function named checking for container termination (*CFCT*) has been defined in the Alarm-Trigger to evaluate if one of the running container instances can be terminated without any application performance degradation.

An important application-level metric which is used in the operation of the Alarm-Trigger is the service response time. Here we discuss how the threshold (T_{res}) for this metric should be set. In order to make the system avoid any performance drop, the value of T_{res} should be set more than the usual time to process a single job without any issue when the system is not overloaded. In the case that T_{res} is set very close to the value of the usual time to process a single job, the auto-scaling method may lead to unnecessary changes in the number of running container instances, whereas the system is currently able to provide users an appropriate performance without any threat. Also, if T_{res} is set too much bigger than the value of the usual time to process a single job, the auto-scaling method will be less sensitive to application performance and more dependent on infrastructure utilization.

Some cloud resource management systems [34–39] use the value of 80% as the primitive threshold for the utilization of CPU and memory (T_{CPU} and T_{mem}). If the value of these two thresholds is set closer to 100%, then the auto-scaling method has no chance to react to runtime variations in the workload before a performance issue arises. If the value of these two thresholds is set less than 80%, then this may lead to an over-provisioning problem which wastes costly resources. If the workload trend is very even and predictable, these two thresholds can be pushed higher than 80%.

According to *CFCI* (shown in Function 1), if one of average CPU or memory usage of the cluster (*AvgCpu* or *AvgMem*) exceeds the associated threshold (T_{CPU} or T_{mem} , 80%) and the average response time (*AvgRT*) is over T_{res} , the number of containers in the cluster needs to increase on demand. Involving the average response time in this function tends to prevent ~20% ($100 - T_{CPU}$ or $100 - T_{mem}$) resources waste. It means there is the possibility that the system may work at even 100% resource utilization without launching more containers, because the average response time is thoroughly satisfying, or in other words, below the T_{res} . In *CFCI*, *cpu_usage_of_container* and *memory_usage_of_container* numbered from 1 to N are the CPU and memory usage of each individual container in the cluster. For example, *cpu_usage_of_container1* is the CPU usage of the first container, *cpu_usage_of_container2* is the CPU usage of the second container, and so forth. *AVG_Cluster* is the grouping operator applied to calculate the average CPU and memory usage of the cluster nominated as *AvgCpu* and *AvgMem*.

CFCT (shown in Function 2) has been specified to check the feasibility of decreasing the number of running container instances, without any QoS degradation perceived by users. In order to improve the stability of the system and to make sure that the system offers a favourable service quality to end-users, it is assumed that if a container is initiated and

added to the cluster, there should not be any container termination during the next two adaptation intervals, even if the average CPU or memory usage of the cluster is quite low.

The Alarm-Trigger component is able to fetch a YAML file which includes all the inputs mentioned in two aforementioned functions (*CFCI* and *CFCT*). This YAML file is being exposed by the SWITCH Web-based IDE via an API. Instructions for the utilization of our implemented Alarm-Trigger component are explained at GitHub [40] published under the Apache 2 license as a part of the SWITCH project software.

4.4. Self-Adapter

The Self-Adapter is called by the Alarm-Trigger and includes two functions which are responsible for proposing adaptation actions. One function named *CI* (Container Instantiation) is to

Function 1 *CFCI* defined in Alarm-Trigger

Inputs:

T_{cpu} : Threshold for the average CPU usage of the cluster
 T_{mem} : Threshold for the average memory usage of the cluster
 T_{res} : Threshold for the average response time

Outputs:

If it is needed to notify the Self-Adapter in order to prevent under-provisioning

```
Cluster=[Container1,..., ContainerN]
AvgCpu=AVG_Cluster(cpu_usage_of_container1,...,
cpu_usage_of_containerN);
AvgMem=AVG_Cluster(memory_usage_of_container1,...,
memory_usage_of_containerN);
if (((AvgCpu>=T_cpu) or (AvgMem>=T_mem)) and
(AvgRT>T_res)) then call ContainerInitiation(); // call CI() to
start new containers
```

Function 2 *CFCT* defined in Alarm-Trigger

Inputs:

T_{cpu} : Threshold for the average CPU usage of the cluster
 T_{mem} : Threshold for the average memory usage of the cluster

Outputs:

If it is needed to notify the Self-Adapter in order to prevent over-provisioning

```
Cluster=[Container1,..., ContainerN]
AvgCpu=AVG_Cluster(cpu_usage_of_container1,...,
cpu_usage_of_containerN);
AvgMem=AVG_Cluster(memory_usage_of_container1,...,
memory_usage_of_containerN);
if (((AvgCpu<T_cpu) or (AvgMem<T_mem)) and (no container
addition in the last two intervals)) then call
ContainerTermination(); // call CT() to stop one of
containers if possible
```

initiate new container instances to improve the performance of the application. Another function named *CT* (Container Termination) is in charge of possibly terminating container instances to avoid resource over-provisioning.

The pseudocode of the proposed *CI* function, defined in the Self-Adapter, is illustrated in Function 3.

CI function starts predicting the average CPU and memory usage of the cluster with regard to ‘current number of containers,’ ‘current average resource usage of the cluster,’ and ‘the amount of increase in the rate of throughput’ if one or more new container instance would be added to the cluster. Based on predicted values (P_{CPU} and P_{mem}) for the average CPU and memory usage of the cluster, the number of new containers that need to be added to the cluster is calculated. If more than one container instance is needed to be initiated, the Self-Adapter runs all required containers concurrently. Therefore, the

Function 3 *CI* defined in Self-Adapter

Inputs:

T_{cpu} : Threshold for the average CPU usage of the cluster
 T_{mem} : Threshold for the average memory usage of the cluster
AvgCpu: Current average CPU usage of the cluster
AvgMem: Current average memory usage of the cluster
 AT_i : Application throughput in the current interval per container
 AT_{i-1} : Application throughput in the last interval per container
 AT_{i-2} : Application throughput in the second last interval per container
cont: Current number of running container instances in the cluster

Outputs:

Launching new container instance(s)

```
inc1 ← 0;
if (AvgCpu>T_cpu) then {
  do {
    inc1++;
    P_cpu ←  $\left( \frac{cont \times AvgCpu \times \left[ \left( 2 \times \frac{AT_i}{AT_{i-1}} + \frac{AT_{i-1}}{AT_{i-2}} \right) / 3 \right]}{cont + inc1} \right)$ ;
  } while (P_cpu>T_cpu);
} // end of if
inc2 ← 0;
if (AvgMem>T_mem) then {
  do {
    inc2++;
    P_mem ←  $\left( \frac{cont \times AvgMem \times \left[ \left( 2 \times \frac{AT_i}{AT_{i-1}} + \frac{AT_{i-1}}{AT_{i-2}} \right) / 3 \right]}{cont + inc2} \right)$ ;
  } while (P_mem>T_mem);
} // end of if
inc ← max(inc1, inc2);
initiate_new_containers(inc); // start ‘inc’ new container(s)
```

adaptation interval (the period when the next adaptation action happens) should be set longer than a container instance's start-up time. In this way, if any auto-scaling event takes place, the whole system is able to continue operating properly without losing control over running container instances.

Here we explain how the termination of non-required containers for a CPU-intensive application happens. Let us suppose that the number of containers in the cluster is two. If the average CPU utilization of the cluster that includes these two containers is less than $\left(\frac{T_{cpu}}{2}\right) - \alpha$, one of the running containers should be terminated. In this formula, α is a constant with values between 0% and 10%, which helps the auto-scaling method conservatively make sure that the container termination will not result in an unstable situation.

Experimenting with equal workload density and computational requirements, an up to 10% difference in the average CPU and memory usage of the cluster (*AvgCpu* or *AvgMem*) can still be observed. This difference is a consequence of runtime variations in running conditions that are out of the application providers' control. Due to this rationale, we have set the maximum value for α at 10%.

A value of α closer to 0% may fail to provide the expected robustness of auto-scaling methodology. Since due to minor fluctuations in the average CPU utilization of around $\left(\frac{T_{cpu}}{2}\right)$, the system may stop a container instance at that moment, and afterwards shortly would start a new one again. A value α closer to 10% may decrease the efficiency of the adaptation method because, in this case, unnecessary container instances generally have less possibility of being eliminated from the cluster. Consequently, a higher value of α would result in longer periods of over-provisioned resources. For the experimentation in this study, we have set the value of α to 5%, which causes neither too frequent changes in the number of running container instances, nor excessive over-provisioning of resources.

Therefore, given that two containers are running in the cluster, if the average CPU usage of the cluster is less than $\left(\frac{80}{2}\right) - 5 = 35$ percent, it is possible to stop one of the running containers. This is so because with the current workload density after the container termination, the average CPU utilization of the cluster would be at most ~70%, which is less than T_{cpu} at 80%. In similar fashion, it was assumed that if there are three running containers and the average CPU usage of the cluster is under $\left(\frac{(3-1) * T_{cpu}}{3}\right) - \alpha$, one of the containers could be stopped, as in this way there would not be any performance issue.

In general, it was presumed if the current number of running containers in the cluster is *cont*, and the average CPU utilization of the cluster is below β_{CPU} defined by Equation (1), it is possible to terminate one of the running containers in the cluster without compromising the QoS of the application. Moreover, for a memory-intensive application, β_{mem} , which is entirely similar to β_{CPU} , helps to define the possibility of decreasing the number of container instances in the cluster if needed upon the memory usage, as Equation (2).

$$\beta_{CPU} = \left(\frac{(cont - 1) * T_{cpu}}{cont} \right) - \alpha \quad (1)$$

$$\beta_{mem} = \left(\frac{(cont - 1) * T_{mem}}{cont} \right) - \alpha \quad (2)$$

The pseudocode of the proposed *CT* function, defined in the Self-Adapter, called by the Alarm-Trigger, is presented in Function 4. According to the average CPU and memory usage of the cluster, this function determines if it is necessary to decrease the number of containers running in the cluster.

The auto-scaling method ensures the application QoS by terminating at most one container in each adaptation interval. In this way, after any container termination, the proposed *CT* function certainly offers acceptable responses within continuously changing, uncertain environments at runtime. For example, this strategy can be used to handle on-off workload scenarios in which peak spikes occur periodically in short time intervals. An example of an on-off workload scenario is shown in Fig. 7.

In these types of workload scenarios, terminating most of the running containers at once when the number of requests instantly decreases a lot is not an appropriate adaptation action because more container instances running into the pool of resources will be necessary very soon. This non-conservative strategy may result in too many container terminations and instantiations with the consequent QoS degradation. In other words, the shutdown and start-up times of containers should be taken into account during on/off workload scenarios.

Function 4 *CT* defined in Self-Adapter

Inputs:

T_{cpu} : Threshold for the average CPU usage of the cluster
 T_{mem} : Threshold for the average memory usage of the cluster
AvgCpu: Current average CPU usage of the cluster
AvgMem: Current average memory usage of the cluster
cont: Current number of running container instances in the cluster
 α : Conservative constant to avoid an unstable situation

Outputs:

Terminating an unnecessary container instance if it is possible

```

dec1 ← 0;
 $\beta_{CPU} \leftarrow \text{Calculate}(T_{cpu}, cont, \alpha)$ ;
if (AvgCpu <  $\beta_{CPU}$ ) then dec1 ← 1;
dec2 ← 0;
 $\beta_{mem} \leftarrow \text{Calculate}(T_{mem}, cont, \alpha)$ ;
if (AvgMem <  $\beta_{mem}$ ) then dec2 ← 1;
dec ← min(dec1, dec2);
if (dec == 1) then terminate_one_container(); // Stop one container

```

FIGURE 7. On-off workload pattern.

5. RESULTS

In our empirical evaluation, the *httperf*¹⁴ tool has been used to develop a load generator in order to produce various workload patterns for different analyses. To this end, five different workload scenarios have been inspected, as shown in Fig. 8.

Each workload pattern examined in this work represents different type of applications. A slowly rising/falling pattern may imply incoming task requests sent to an e-learning system in which daytime includes more traffic than at night. A drastically changing pattern may represent a heavy workload to be processed by a broadcasting news channel in which a video or some news suddenly spreads in the social media world. This type of system generally has a short active period, after which the service can be provided at the lowest service level. Applications such as batch processing systems accomplish workload scenarios similar to the on-off workload pattern in which requests tend to be accumulated around batch runs regularly over short periods of time. A gently shaking pattern indicates predictable environments such as household settings that allow application providers to specify detailed requirements, and then allocate the exact amount of resources to the system.

Our proposed method called the ‘DM’ auto-scaling approach has been compared with different rule-based provisioning policies explained in Section 2.2. These approaches include HPA (Horizontal Pod Auto-scaling), TTS1 (Target Tracking Scaling—first method), TTS2 (Target Tracking Scaling—second method), SS1 (Step Scaling—first method), SS2 (Step Scaling—second method), THRES1 (THRESHOLD—first method) and THRES2 (THRESHOLD—second method). We kept the implementation of all these auto-scaling approaches and experimental data available at GitHub [41]. However, we did not implement MP, as this provisioning policy is not revealed clearly in terms of technical feasibility by Google Cloud Platform.

Each experiment has been repeated for five iterations to find the average values of significant properties and to verify the achieved results and hence to reach a greater validity of

FIGURE 8. Experiment design to compare the new DM method to existing auto-scaling methods.

results. Therefore, the reported results are mean values over five runs for each experiment.

In every experiment, each auto-scaling method has been investigated primarily based on the 95th percentile of the response time, the median response time, average number of containers, average CPU usage and average memory usage.

Since the workload trends examined in our experiments are considered neither even nor predictable, the thresholds T_{CPU} and T_{mem} are set to 80%. Hence, the DM method will have enough chance to react to runtime variations in the workload because these thresholds are not very close to 100%. This fact will also prevent an over-provisioning problem because these thresholds are not less than 80%. The constant α is set to the value of 5 which can prevent not only too frequent changes in the number of running container instances, but also too much over-provisioning of resources according to the rationale explained in Section 4.4.

A finite element analysis application useful for solving engineering and mathematical physics problems has been developed and containerized to be used in this work as a use case [1]. In our use case, a single job usually takes 180 ms with our experimental setup in situations where the system is not overloaded. For the DM method, in order to avoid performance drop, the response time threshold (T_{res}) has been set to 190 ms that is neither very close to the value of usual time to process a single job (180 ms) nor much bigger than this value. Therefore, the DM auto-scaling method will be responsive to changes in not only infrastructure utilization, but also application response time because T_{res} is not much bigger than the usual time to process a single job.

¹⁴<https://github.com/httperf/httperf>

When it comes to response time guarantees, determining the difference between auto-scaling methods in capability of providing response time under different workload patterns is considered informative. To this end, as shown in Table 4, DM was compared with all other methods using paired Student's *t*-tests with respect to all response time values over the experimental period for each workload pattern ($n = 145$). The 95th percentile value of response time, shown in Table 5, is an indicator of the auto-scaling methods' ability to deliver QoS according to a service level agreement (SLA). The median response time achieved by all investigated auto-scaling methods in every workload pattern is shown in Table 6.

Table 7 presents the resource utilization of all auto-scaling methods for all workload patterns in terms of average number of containers, average CPU usage and average memory usage. In this table, there is a column called resource utilization function which equals to the average number of containers multiplied by the 95th percentile of the response time achieved by auto-scaling methods for each workload pattern. It should be noted that in order to improve the resource utilization of an auto-scaling method while producing acceptable response time, the value of this function should be decreased as much as possible.

Our experiments show that the period of time taken to start up a container instance is almost 6 s. In the experiments, the adaptation interval, which is the time period between two possible successive adaptation events (increasing or decreasing the number of cluster nodes), was defined as 30 s to make sure there would be no problem if any auto-scaling action occurs. While the monitoring interval can be specified as very short in milliseconds, it is set to 30 s to reduce the communication traffic load and any monitoring overhead for the measurements.

Table 8 shows the features of all machines used in our experiments. All these machines belong to a non-profit cloud-based infrastructure provider called ARNES (the Academic and Research Network of Slovenia). In our experiments, all host machines allocated to the cluster which provides the finite element analysis application have the same hardware features. Twelve hosts have been used in the cluster during the experiments.

5.1. Slowly rising/falling workload pattern

In this scenario as shown in Fig. 9, the workload includes two steps. In the first step of the workload scenario, the

TABLE 4. *P*-values obtained by comparison of the DM method with other seven auto-scaling methods using paired *t*-tests with respect to all response time values over the experimental period for each workload pattern.

Workload scenario	HPA	THRES1	THRES2	SS1	SS2	TTS1	TTS2
Slowly rising/falling	0.18800	0.14650	0.75633	0.00568	0.00033	0.00118	0.00009
Drastically changing	0.00055	0.00000	0.00000	0.00385	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000
On-off	0.00000	0.00191	0.00115	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000
Gently shaking	0.00032	0.15528	0.00004	0.00051	0.63366	0.00000	0.00000
Real-world	0.00014	0.00718	0.00001	0.00000	0.00005	0.00424	0.00000

TABLE 5. The 95th percentile of the response time achieved by all investigated auto-scaling methods in every workload pattern.

Workload scenario	HPA	THRES1	THRES2	SS1	SS2	TTS1	TTS2	DM
Slowly rising/falling	213.07	202.40	208.21	364.70	372.90	365.20	398.90	207.40
Drastically changing	652.82	659.90	619.20	852.06	1623.14	1609.22	1270.98	410.28
On-off	471.75	386.00	387.90	683.70	493.60	550.40	566.50	232.60
Gently shaking	201.83	196.04	195.89	194.80	195.00	268.69	240.47	194.85
Real-world	204.64	208.84	214.26	202.94	233.64	215.66	260.2	197.32

TABLE 6. The median response time achieved by all investigated auto-scaling methods in every workload pattern.

Workload scenario	HPA	THRES1	THRES2	SS1	SS2	TTS1	TTS2	DM
Slowly rising/falling	190.6	189.6	188.7	190.7	192.9	189.6	192.1	191.2
Drastically changing	185.6	193.0	199.1	190.5	197.9	199.4	201.0	190.1
On-off	199.6	191.3	195.5	194.5	200.7	209.7	211.4	190.5
Gently shaking	189.9	186.1	188.7	187.9	184.9	196.1	196.7	185.3
Real-world	193.4	192.0	194.4	195.3	193.9	195.3	197.4	192.3

TABLE 7. Comparing the new DM method with existing auto-scaling methods with respect to resource utilization.

Workload scenario	Method	Resource utilization			Resource utilization function
		Average number of containers	Average CPU usage	Average memory usage	
Slowly rising/falling pattern	DM	3.47	64.36	31.55	719.68
	HPA	3.25	65.48	31.60	692.48
	THRES1	3.65	62.24	31.50	738.76
	THRES2	3.52	64.84	31.64	732.90
	SS1	4.36	55.85	31.57	1590.09
	SS2	3.84	61.86	31.73	1431.94
	TTS1	3.12	71.85	31.56	1139.42
	TTS2	3.32	70.78	31.58	1324.35
Drastically changing pattern	DM	3.71	41.07	31.69	1522.14
	HPA	2.50	50.77	31.68	1632.05
	THRES1	3.31	40.72	31.58	2184.27
	THRES2	3.31	40.92	31.51	2049.55
	SS1	3.53	41.54	31.43	3007.77
	SS2	2.47	45.22	31.68	4009.15
	TTS1	2.68	45.69	31.63	4312.71
	TTS2	2.68	45.84	31.71	3406.23
On-off pattern	DM	3.58	53.49	31.40	832.71
	HPA	2.77	66.90	31.50	1306.75
	THRES1	3.39	57.25	31.55	1308.54
	THRES2	3.40	58.27	31.74	1318.86
	SS1	3.23	51.50	31.61	2208.35
	SS2	2.71	58.53	31.72	1337.66
	TTS1	2.33	64.90	31.69	1282.43
	TTS2	2.33	64.65	31.70	1319.94
Gently shaking pattern	DM	4.00	66.67	31.75	779.40
	HPA	3.78	70.46	31.80	762.92
	THRES1	4.00	66.94	31.58	784.16
	THRES2	3.68	72.10	31.61	720.87
	SS1	4.25	64.31	31.49	827.90
	SS2	4.00	67.74	31.76	780.00
	TTS1	3.41	79.25	31.62	916.23
	TTS2	3.38	78.95	31.63	812.79
Real-world pattern	DM	10.15	72.38	31.59	2002.80
	HPA	9.20	75.81	31.55	1882.69
	THRES1	9.86	71.02	31.61	2059.16
	THRES2	9.98	70.32	31.56	2138.31
	SS1	10.16	73.15	31.60	2061.87
	SS2	9.38	74.23	31.59	2191.54
	TTS1	7.27	79.09	31.60	1567.85
	TTS2	7.64	75.44	31.62	1987.92

number of incoming requests slowly rises from 100 to 1500 requests per 6 s. Afterwards, during the second step, workload density drops smoothly from 1500 to 100 requests. Figure 9 shows that the number of containers increases in the first step of the workload scenario, and it decreases in the second step

according to the number of arrived requests at execution time by all eight provisioning methods.

For the slowly rising/falling workload pattern, the paired *t*-tests comparing DM with HPA, THRES1 and THRES2 reveal no statistically significant difference with $P > 0.01$. While all

TABLE 8. Features of infrastructures used in our experiments.

Feature	Load-Balancer	Monitoring Server	Hosts in the cluster
OS	Ubuntu 14.04	Ubuntu 14.04	Ubuntu 14.04
CPU(s)	4	2	4
CPU MHz	2397	2397	3100
Memory	16 384 MB	4096 MB	4096 MB
Speed	1000 Mbps	1000 Mbps	1000 Mbps

auto-scaling approaches are able to provide acceptable performance on average, the response time offered by SS1, SS2, TTS1 and TTS2 is sometimes low in comparison to DM, HPA, THRES1 and THRES2. This is because the adaptation interval used in SS1, SS2, TTS1 and TTS2 is 1 minute versus 30 s used in DM, HPA, THRES1 and THRES2. Hence, the response time can be inappropriate for a while in some situations if the adaptation interval is not short enough, as shown in Fig. 10. This fact resulted in relatively weaker performance of SS1, SS2, TTS1 and TTS2 compared to DM, HPA, THRES1 and THRES2 with regard to the 95th percentile values.

The length of the adaptation interval, whether 30 s or 1 minute, used by auto-scaling methods affects the overall application performance. For example when $t = 90$ s and before the CPU run queue would start filling up ($\sim 96\%$), DM decided to allocate one new container because of the increase in the workload. Therefore, the response time offered by DM was not affected by the workload increase. Considering another auto-scaling method called SS1, in such situation when $t = 120$ s and after the system was overloaded as a consequence of the growing workload, SS1 added four new containers to the cluster. However, at this time the processor utilization already reached almost 100%, and hence the slow response time was provided by SS1 for a while. Now the cluster includes five container instances. This cluster size is more than what is needed to handle the current workload. Therefore, this decision is reverted after a while when $t = 240$ s, and two container instances are terminated.

It should be noted that DM, HPA, THRES1 and THRES2 use almost the same number of container instances and have almost the same level of average resource utilization in terms of CPU and memory usage for the slowly rising/falling workload pattern. The SS1 provisioning approach allocated more container instances (4.36) compared to all other adaptation policies.

Moreover, the authors simply concluded that the finite element analysis application is not memory-intensive, as the average memory usage was almost steady during the conducted experiment, and the same for all auto-scaling approaches—around $\sim 31\%$ of the whole memory.

5.2. Drastically changing workload pattern

Here, drastic fluctuations appear in the workload intensity. In this experiment, shown in Fig. 11, the number of arrival

FIGURE 10. Average response time of the application in response to a slowly rising/falling workload pattern.

requests changes suddenly from 100 to 1500, and after a while it instantly comes back to 100 requests again. For this workload pattern, the paired t-tests implied that there is a statistically significant difference between DM and all other auto-scaling methods. Figure 11 shows that our proposed method (DM) properly recognized the sudden increase in the workload and then tried to timely initiate enough container instances at the beginning of unexpected workload surge faster than other auto-scaling approaches. Therefore, for the drastically changing workload pattern, DM is the only method able to provide relatively convenient performance in terms of the 95th percentile of the response time distribution.

After a while, when the workload immediately drops again to 100 requests per 6 s, all auto-scaling approaches, except HPA and SS1, do not stop container instances running in the

cluster at once, and consequently the number of containers slightly decreases in successive intervals. The method which provisioned more container instances than other auto-scaling approaches was DM. The average number of containers allocated by DM during this experiment was 3.71.

Figure 12 shows that the response time provided by DM, compared to other approaches, is less inappropriately impacted by the drastic change in the workload density.

Again, the amount of average memory usage was nearly constant ($\sim 31\%$ of the memory capacity), and the same for all auto-scaling approaches during the whole conducted experiment in this workload scenario, considered as further confirmation of a slowly rising/falling workload scenario's result, implying that the conducted application is not a memory-intensive benchmark.

5.3. On-off workload pattern

In this experiment, the on-off workload pattern has three active periods. The active periods include, respectively, 1500, 1200 and 700 requests per 6 s (shown in Fig. 13). Inactive periods between peak spikes are 30 s. For the on-off workload pattern, the paired t -tests showed a statistically significant difference in the means of response time metric offered by all auto-scaling methods. The only method able to timely provision an appropriate number of container instances in response to peak spikes is DM. Because it is more agile than other auto-scaling approaches in order to initiate necessary container instances at the beginning of unexpected workload surges, and also it does not terminate most of the containers immediately when each peak spike disappears. Consequently, DM has allocated more container instances on average (3.58) than other approaches during the on-off workload pattern.

FIGURE 11. Dynamically changing number of container instances in response to a drastically changing workload pattern.

The advantage of using 30-s adaptation interval instead of one-minute interval can be understood in Fig. 13. At the beginning of the first active period, DM and SS1 took similar decision to increase the number of containers because of the sudden increase in the workload. DM allocated three extra containers starting from $t = 90$ s whereas SS1 allocated four new containers when the system is already overloaded at $t = 120$ s, or in other words 30 s later than $t = 90$ s. In such situation, the competence of DM compared to SS1 exists in its agility to timely adapt the application performance to the sudden increase in the workload. As a consequence, in this workload scenario the difference between DM and SS1 in terms of response time can be considered enormous. That is why the

FIGURE 12. Average response time of the application in response to a drastically changing workload pattern.

FIGURE 13. Dynamically changing number of container instances in response to an on-off workload pattern.

worst response times provided by DM and SS1 during the first active period were 225.04 ms versus 558.88 ms, respectively.

For the on-off workload pattern, the median and the 95th percentile of the response time provided by DM in this experiment were 191.2 and 232.60 ms, respectively, that can be considered acceptable with regard to users' satisfaction. Whereas sudden active periods inappropriately cause an increase in the service time of the requests for the other seven auto-scaling methods, as shown in Fig. 14. Compared to the DM method, the 95th percentile values of the response time achieved by all other auto-scaling methods are very slow that can be considered inappropriate.

In this experiment, the average memory usage was found to be consistent ($\sim 31\%$) for all auto-scaling methods, and it did not vary with the increase in the number of requests at runtime.

5.4. Gently shaking workload pattern

In this scenario, there exists a trembling workload which does not change drastically. As shown in Fig. 15, it frequently varies between 700 and 1000 requests to be processed by the application. Figure 15 indicates that if the workload does not change drastically, there is neither increment nor decrement in the number of running containers for DM, THRES1 and SS2. This is why, for this workload pattern, the paired t-tests comparing DM with THRES1 and SS2 showed that we cannot reject the zero hypothesis ($P > 0.01$), essentially meaning that the DM method behaves the same way as the THRES1 and SS2 methods. The number of containers has also not been changed to a great extent by other approaches namely HPA, THRES2, SS1, TTS1, and TTS2.

The SS1 auto-scaling policy allocated more container instances on average (4.25) than other approaches, whereas the average response time provided by all provisioning

approaches (shown in Fig. 16) was nearly steady and identical for this workload scenario.

Therefore, allocating more container instances by SS1 in this workload scenario undesirably caused resource under-utilization, in terms of less average CPU resource utilization, and reported 64.31% in comparison to what was achieved by other methods. However, all auto-scaling approaches achieved approximately the same level of memory usage ($\sim 31\%$) during the experiment.

5.5. Real-world workload pattern

In addition to the previous workload patterns, in order to validate the applicability of our proposed approach against real-world situations, FIFA World Cup 98 workload dataset [42] has been also applied in this work. This workload trace has been widely used in different auto-scaling research works [7, 43–47] so far. For our experiment, we used a 20-minute trace (shown in Fig. 17) on the 12 July 1998 starting at 20:30:00. The number of incoming requests per 6 s is varied between 2112 and 2858 during this time period that represents a large variance (~ 750) in the workload density at runtime.

To adapt the application to the changing workload and achieve a desired performance, the number of running container instances allocated by auto-scaling methods varies over time. DM and SS1 provisioned the same amount of resources in terms of container instances on average for the real-world workload pattern. For both methods, the average number of containers was equal to 10.1. Other methods allocated fewer container instances compared to DM and SS1 in this experiment.

Figure 18 shows the average response time provided by all investigated auto-scaling methods in response to this real-world workload pattern.

FIGURE 14. Average response time of the application in response to an on-off workload pattern.

FIGURE 15. Dynamically changing number of container instances in response to a gently shaking workload pattern.

For the real-world workload pattern, the response time offered by DM was not affected by the workload variations, since it was quite steady in comparison to what was provided by other approaches. In other words, there is no big difference between the 95th percentile of the response time distribution (197.32 ms) and the median response time (192.3 ms) obtained by DM.

Similar to the result concluded in previous workload patterns, the experiment in this scenario also re-implies that the memory resource utilization of the cluster does not have any influence on the performance of the finite element analysis application regardless of the number of incoming requests, because, it was $\sim 31\%$ for all auto-scaling methods during execution. This fact fortunately helps the cloud-based service provider to achieve efficient memory allocation for running container instances in advance.

FIGURE 16. Average response time of the application in response to a gently shaking workload pattern.

FIGURE 17. Dynamically changing number of container instances in response to a real-world workload pattern.

For each auto-scaling method, all values of resource utilization functions achieved in every workload pattern were summed together to form an overall score. The scores are DM = 5856.73, HPA = 6276.89, THRES1 = 7074.89, THRES2 = 6960.49, SS1 = 9695.98, SS2 = 9750.29, TTS1 = 9218.65 and TTS2 = 8851.23. These results show that the DM auto-scaling method is the best among eight investigated approaches. This is because our proposed DM auto-scaling approach achieved the minimum overall score in comparison to the other approaches. It means that it is able to avoid over-provisioning of resources while offering optimal application performance in terms of the response time. Considering all workload scenarios examined in this work, the strength of the DM method lies in its ability to apply a multi-level monitoring framework and timely adjust itself to changes in the workload density over time.

The cumulative distribution function (CDF) of response time observed by all auto-scaling methods is shown from Fig. 19 to Fig. 23 for each workload pattern. It can be concluded that DM performs better than other methods as it has higher probability to offer desired response time under varied amount of workloads, and hence improve the application QoS. The probability that the response time provided by DM would be slow is approximately zero for all workload scenarios, except for the drastically changing pattern. Figure 20 shows that the response time provided by DM was relatively more appropriate than other seven auto-scaling methods during the drastically changing workload. In this workload scenario, the probability of response time being fast provided by other methods is significantly small.

6. DISCUSSION

The obtained results allow analysis of the developed auto-scaling method and its limitations, its usability in the software

FIGURE 18. Average response time of the application in response to a real-world workload pattern.

FIGURE 19. CDF of response time observed for the slowly rising/falling workload pattern.

FIGURE 21. CDF of response time observed for the on-off workload pattern.

FIGURE 20. CDF of response time observed for the drastically changing workload pattern.

FIGURE 22. CDF of response time observed for the gently shaking workload pattern.

engineering domain, comparisons with other rule-based methods, and the level of improvement in the effectiveness of self-adaptation for handling different workload scenarios.

An important part which has been investigated is the monitoring interval. Setting up an appropriate monitoring interval is required to ensure the reliability of the whole system, to avoid overhead, and to prevent losing control over the running environment during auto-scaling actions [48]. Defining an effective measurement interval is a challenging task, because a low level of measurement ratio may lead to missing dynamic changes of operational environments, and hence the system is not capable of adapting to a new situation to continue its operation without any performance issue.

In some cases, the difference between the monitoring interval and the average response time of the application may cause stability issues to the elasticity mechanism, which is not the case for many applications such as finite element analysis. For example, within video conferencing systems, violations of QoS constraints need to be monitored carefully, since even a small amount of violation should not be disregarded. Therefore, the monitoring interval should be short enough to adequately capture all necessary characteristics of the application over time. Moreover, self-adaptation of such applications also requires a high level of agility, which has recently gained a wide range of attention as a research field that still needs to be fully improved.

FIGURE 23. CDF of response time observed for the real-world workload pattern.

The proposed method can be extended to also consider vertical scaling of containers [49]. Vertical scaling is an option to resize processing power, memory capacity, or bandwidth assigned to container instances depending on runtime workload variations. However, the maximum amount of resources such as CPU or memory available for each container is limited to the host machine capacity. Therefore, the combination of vertical and horizontal scaling techniques can be applied to the same application in order to take advantages of both mechanisms. However, it should be noted that some applications such as Java/J2EE solutions [50] are not able to dynamically manage the memory allocation even if the memory capacity can be resized at the infrastructure or operating system (OS) level. In such cases, the applications have to be restarted with new resized memory when vertical scaling occurs.

The experiments in this work are based on Docker technology, however the proposed auto-scaling architecture can be implemented in other containerization technologies such as OpenVZ,¹⁵ LXC¹⁶ and lmcify.¹⁷ This is because all functions defined in both Alarm-Trigger and Self-Adapter, as well as the StatsD protocol used to send, collect, and aggregate monitoring statistics related to any application or infrastructure, are independent from not only container virtualization technologies, but also underlying cloud infrastructure providers.

The implemented multi-level monitoring system of the SWITCH platform used in this work is capable of monitoring different container-level metrics namely CPU, memory, bandwidth, and disk [2]. This monitoring system has been employed to measure bandwidth and disk for a containerized file upload use case in our previous work [51].

Over the entire course of experimentation, different threats to the validity of the results have been analysed as follows:

- Variations in runtime conditions (e.g. time-varying processing delays, I/O and CPU load factors, etc.) may slightly affect the results shown in Table 5. In order to reach a greater validity of results, each experiment on each workload pattern was repeated five times to avoid this threat. Therefore, the reported results are presented as average values over independent runs.
- Cloud infrastructure QoS properties, e.g. availability, bandwidth quality etc. may vary over time, independently of the workload features. Therefore, when a container has to be deployed on a host machine, the application provider needs to make sure that the host is able to fulfil the requirements of the containerized application. To this end, the performance of infrastructures should also be continuously characterized. This is currently facilitated by the employed multi-level monitoring system of the SWITCH platform.
- Various additional external factors (e.g. end-users' network channel diversity, unstable network conditions at the client's side and the mobility of the clients) may affect the users' experience. In reality, cloud-based services are being used by different end-users from all over the world. This type of quality problems due to connectivity issues are currently being addressed by edge computing approaches [2].
- Proposing a container-based auto-scaling method without relying on over-provisioning of resources is an important challenge in the adaptation of cloud-based applications. The principle which allows host machines to include one container instance per application type (e.g. CPU, memory, or bandwidth intensive), explained in Section 3.3, may cause over-provisioning among some clusters when there are applications which experience a small number of incoming requests. To come up with a solution to solve this limitation, in addition to the containers, host machines can be also adjusted vertically at runtime [52]. Another solution can be using different host machines in terms of hardware features allocated for each cluster according to the application types. For example, hardware characteristics of nodes which host a CPU-intensive application can be different from configurations of nodes which host a memory-intensive application. The former needs host machines with sufficient CPU, and the later requires host machines with enough memory.

7. CONCLUSION

Fine-grained auto-scaling mechanisms are needed to cope with highly dynamic workloads in the cloud environment. Existing

¹⁵OpenVZ Linux Containers, <http://openvz.org>

¹⁶LXC, <http://www.ibm.com/developerworks/linux/library/l-lxc-containers>

¹⁷lmcify, <https://github.com/google/lmcify>

traditional application adaptation approaches using a set of fixed rules unfortunately cannot accurately provide favourable service quality while offering optimal resource utilization. This paper introduced a new DM auto-scaling method which applies dynamic rules to automatically increase or decrease the total number of computing instances in order to accommodate varied workloads.

The proposed adaptation method innovatively uses a multi-level monitoring system since the adaption of containerized applications should be tuned and handled at various levels of cloud environments—container level and application level. The conducted experiments have demonstrated the benefits of our approach which can be considered the best among eight investigated auto-scaling methods. Particular benefits of using the proposed DM method are that it avoids under-provisioning as well as over-provisioning of resources, while it prevents QoS degradation and cost overruns at execution time.

We have begun extending our proposed method towards a multi-instance architecture and high level of service customization [53]. This architecture applies one application instance per one user or one type of users. It means there are different application instances for different users with various needs. In this model, any self-adaptation mechanism would need to consider more sophisticated options, such as setting up a new monitoring environment for a different type of application instance, which will add to the complexity of the adaptation process for the application.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are thankful to the Academic and Research Network of Slovenia (ARNES) for use of their public cloud infrastructure.

FUNDING

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No. 643963 (SWITCH project: Software Workbench for Interactive, Time Critical and Highly self-adaptive cloud applications). and grant agreement No. 732339 (PrEstoCloud: Proactive Cloud Resources Management at the Edge for Efficient Real-Time Big Data Processing).

REFERENCES

- [1] Juzna, J., Cesarek, P., Petcu, D. and Stankovski, V. (2014) Solving solid and fluid mechanics problems in the cloud with moSAiC. *Comput. Sci. Eng.*, **16**(3), 68–77.
- [2] Taherizadeh, S., Jones, A.C., Taylor, I., Zhao, Z. and Stankovski, V. (2018) Monitoring self-adaptive applications within edge computing frameworks: A state-of-the-art review. *J. Syst. Softw.*, **136**, 19–38.
- [3] Abdelbaky, M., Diaz-Montes, J., Parashar, M., Unuvar, M. and Steinder, M. (2015) Docker containers across multiple clouds and data centers. *Proc. 2015 IEEE/ACM 8th Int. Conf. Utility and Cloud Computing (UCC)*, Limassol, Cyprus, 7–10 Dec., pp. 368–371. IEEE.
- [4] Al-Sharif, Z.A., Jararweh, Y., Al-Dahoud, A. and Alawneh, L. M. (2016) ACCRS: autonomic based cloud computing resource scaling. *Cluster Comput.*, **20**(3), 2479–2488.
- [5] Islam, S., Keung, J., Lee, K. and Liu, A. (2012) Empirical prediction models for adaptive resource provisioning in the cloud. *Future Gener. Comput. Syst.*, **28**(1), 155–162.
- [6] Jamshidi, P., Sharifloo, A.M., Pahl, C., Metzger, A. and Estrada, G. (2015) Self-Learning Cloud Controllers: Fuzzy Q-Learning for Knowledge Evolution. *Proc. Int. Conf. Cloud and Autonomic Computing (ICCAC)*, Boston, USA, 21–25 Sept., pp. 208–211. IEEE.
- [7] Arabnejad, H., Pahl, C., Jamshidi, P. and Estrada, G. (2017) A Comparison of Reinforcement Learning Techniques for Fuzzy Cloud Auto-Scaling. *Proc. 17th IEEE/ACM International Symposium on Cluster, Cloud and Grid Computing*, Madrid, Spain, 14–17 May, pp. 64–73. ACM.
- [8] Tsoumakos, D., Konstantinou, I., Boumpouka, C., Sioutas, S. and Koziris, N. (2013) Automated, elastic resource provisioning for NoSQL clusters using TIRAMOLA. *Proc. 2013 13th IEEE/ACM International Symposium on Cluster, Cloud and Grid Computing (CCGrid)*, Delft, Netherlands, 13–16 May, pp. 1–8. IEEE.
- [9] Gandhi, A., Dube, P., Karve, A., Kochut, A. and Zhang, L. (2014) Adaptive, Model-driven Autoscaling for Cloud Applications. *Proc. 11th Int. Conf. Autonomic Computing (ICAC'14)*, Philadelphia, PA, 18–20 June, pp. 57–64. USENIX.
- [10] Baresi, L., Guinea, S., Leva, A. and Quattrocchi, G. (2016) A discrete-time feedback controller for containerised cloud applications. *Proc. 2016 24th ACM SIGSOFT International Symposium on Foundations of Software Engineering*, New York, NY, 13–18 Nov., pp. 217–228. ACM.
- [11] Dube, P., Gandhi, A., Karve, A., Kochut, A. and Zhang, L. (2016) Scaling a cloud infrastructure. International Business Machines Corporation. Patent no. US 9300552 B2, USA.
- [12] Zhao, Z. *et al.* (2015) Developing and operating time critical applications in clouds: the state of the art and the SWITCH approach. *Proc. 1st Int. Conf. Cloud Forward: From Distributed to Complete Computing*, Pisa, Italy, 6–8 October, pp. 17–28. Elsevier.
- [13] Ghobaei-Arani, M., Jabbehdari, S. and Pourmina, M.A. (2018) An autonomic resource provisioning approach for service-based cloud applications: a hybrid approach. *Future Gener. Comput. Syst.*, **78**(1), 191–210.
- [14] Nikraves, A.Y., Ajila, S.A. and Lung, C.H. (2015) Towards an Autonomic Auto-scaling Prediction System for Cloud Resource Provisioning. *Proc. 2015 IEEE/ACM 10th International Symposium on Software Engineering for Adaptive and Self-Managing Systems*, Florence, Italy, 18–19 May, pp. 35–45. IEEE.
- [15] Aniello, L., Bonomi, S., Lombardi, F., Zelli, A. and Baldoni, R. (2014) An Architecture for Automatic Scaling of Replicated Services. *Proc. 2nd Int. Conf. NETWORKED SYSTEMS (NETYS)*, Marrakech, Morocco, 15–17 May, pp. 122–137. Springer International Publishing.

- [16] Loff, J. and Garcia, J. (2014) Vadara: Predictive Elasticity for Cloud Applications. *Proceedings of 2014 IEEE 6th Int. Conf. Cloud Computing Technology and Science (CloudCom)*, Singapore, Singapore, 15–18 Dec., pp. 541–546. IEEE.
- [17] Kubernetes Horizontal Pod Auto-scaling, <https://kubernetes.io/docs/tasks/run-application/horizontal-pod-autoscale/>. [Online; accessed March 10, 2018].
- [18] Amazon Target Tracking Scaling, <http://docs.aws.amazon.com/autoscaling/latest/userguide/as-scaling-target-tracking.html>. [Online; accessed March 10, 2018].
- [19] Amazon Step Scaling, <https://aws.amazon.com/blogs/aws/auto-scaling-update-new-scaling-policies-for-more-responsive-scaling/>. [Online; accessed March 10, 2018].
- [20] Google Multiple Policies Scaling, <https://cloud.google.com/compute/docs/autoscaler/multiple-policies>. [Online; accessed March 10, 2018].
- [21] Caglar, F. and Gokhale, A. (2014) iOverbook: Intelligent resource overbooking to support soft realtime applications in the cloud. *Proc. 2014 IEEE 7th Int. Conf. Cloud Computing (CLOUD)*, Anchorage, AK, 27 June–2 July, pp. 538–545. IEEE.
- [22] Kwon, S.K. and Noh, J.H. (2013) Implementation of monitoring system for cloud computing. *Int. J. Modern Eng. Res.*, **3** (4), 1916–1918.
- [23] Lei, Z., Hu, B., Guo, J., Hu, L., Shen, W. and Lei, Y. (2014) Scalable and efficient workload hotspot detection in virtualized environment. *Cluster Comput.*, **17**(4), 1253–1264.
- [24] Meera, A. and Swamynathan, S. (2013) Agent based Resource Monitoring System in IaaS Cloud Environment. *Proc. 1st Int. Conf. Computational Intelligence: Modeling Techniques and Applications (CIMTA)*, Kalyani, India, 27–28 September, pp. 200–207. Elsevier.
- [25] Gupta, U. (2015) Monitoring in IOT enabled devices. *Int. J. Adv. Netw. Appl.*, **7**(1), 2622–2625.
- [26] Massie, M.L., Chun, B.N. and Culler, D.E. (2004) The ganglia distributed monitoring system: design, implementation, and experience. *Parallel Comput.*, **30**(7), 817–840.
- [27] Tader, P. (2010) Server monitoring with Zabbix. *Linux J.*, **195**, 7–10.
- [28] Murphy, J.W. (2008) Snoscan: an iterative functionality service scanner for large scale networks. Thesis no.: 1461885, Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Iowa State University, Iowa, USA.
- [29] Clayman, S., Toffetti, G., Galis, A. and Chapman, C. (2012) Monitoring services in a federated cloud: the RESERVOIR experience. In Villari, M., Brandic, I. and Tusa, F. (eds.) *Achieving Federated and Self-Manageable Cloud Infrastructures: Theory and Practice*. IGI Global, USA.
- [30] Katsaros, G., Kubert, R., Gallizo, G. and Wang, T. (2011) Monitoring: a fundamental process to provide QoS guarantees in cloud-based platform. In Benatallah, B. (ed.) *Cloud Computing: Methodology, System, and Applications*. CRC Press, USA.
- [31] Trihinas, D., Pallis, G. and Dikaiakos, M.D. (2014) JCatascopia: Monitoring Elastically Adaptive Applications in the Cloud. *Proc. 14th IEEE/ACM International Symposium on Cluster, Cloud and Grid Computing (CCGrid)*, Chicago, IL, 26–29 May, pp. 226–235. IEEE.
- [32] The SWITCH Monitoring Server container image, https://hub.docker.com/r/salmant/ul_monitoring_server_container_image/. [Online; accessed March 10, 2018].
- [33] The SWITCH monitoring system, <https://github.com/salmant/ASAP/tree/master/SWITCH-Monitoring-System>. [Online; accessed March 10, 2018].
- [34] Han, R., Guo, L., Ghanem, M.M. and Guo, Y. (2012) Lightweight resource scaling for cloud applications. *Proc. 12th IEEE/ACM Int. Symp. Cluster, Cloud and Grid Computing (CCGrid)*, Ottawa, ON, 13–16 May, pp. 644–651. IEEE.
- [35] Lu, Z., Wu, J., Bao, J. and Hung, P.C. (2016) OCRm: OpenStack-based cloud datacentre resource monitoring and management scheme. *Int. J. High Performance Comput. Netw.*, **9**, 31–44.
- [36] Singhi, G. and Tiwari, D. (2017) A load balancing approach for increasing the resource utilisation by minimizing the number of active servers. *Int. J. Comput. Security Source Code Anal.*, **3**, 11–15.
- [37] Alonso, A., Aguado, I., Salvachua, J. and Rodriguez, P. (2016) A Metric to Estimate Resource Use in Cloud-Based Videoconferencing Distributed Systems. *Proc. 2016 IEEE 4th Int. Conf. Future Internet of Things and Cloud (FiCloud)*, Vienna, Austria, 22–24 Aug., pp. 25–32. IEEE.
- [38] Monil, M.A.H. and Rahman, R.M. (2015) Implementation of modified overload detection technique with VM selection strategies based on heuristics and migration control. *Proc. 2015 IEEE/ACIS 14th Int. Conf. Computer and Information Science (ICIS)*, Las Vegas, NV, 28 June–1 July, pp. 223–227. IEEE.
- [39] Alonso, A., Aguado, I., Salvachua, J. and Rodriguez, P. (2017) A methodology for designing and evaluating cloud scheduling strategies in distributed videoconferencing systems. *IEEE Trans. Multimed.*, **19**, 2282–2292.
- [40] The SWITCH Alarm-Trigger component, <https://github.com/salmant/ASAP/tree/master/SWITCH-Alarm-Trigger>. [Online; accessed March 10, 2018].
- [41] The SWITCH Self-Adapter component, <https://github.com/salmant/ASAP/tree/master/SWITCH-Self-Adapter>. [Online; accessed March 10, 2018].
- [42] 1998 World Cup Web Site Access Logs, <http://ita.ee.lbl.gov/html/contrib/WorldCup.html>. [Online; accessed March 10, 2018].
- [43] Rattanaopas, K. and Tandayya, P. (2017) Adaptive workload prediction for cloud-based server infrastructures. *J. Telecommun. Electron. Comput. Eng.*, **9**, 129–134.
- [44] Jiao, L., Tulino, A.M., Llorca, J., Jin, Y. and Sala, A. (2017) Smoothed online resource allocation in multi-tier distributed cloud networks. *IEEE/ACM Trans. Netw.*, **25**, 2556–2570.
- [45] Tran, D., Tran, N., Nguyen, B.M. and Le, H. (2016) PD-GABP—A novel prediction model applying for elastic applications in distributed environment. *Proc. 2016 3rd National Foundation for Science and Technology Development Conference on Information and Computer Science (NICS)*, Danang, Vietnam, September 14–16, pp. 240–245. IEEE.
- [46] Logeswaran, L., Bandara, H.D. and Bhathiyaa, H.S. (2016) Performance, Resource, and Cost Aware Resource Provisioning in the Cloud. *Proc. 2016 IEEE 9th Int. Conf.*

- Cloud Computing (CLOUD)*, San Francisco, CA, 27 June–2 July, pp. 913–916. IEEE.
- [47] Moore, L.R., Bean, K. and Ellahi, T. (2013) A coordinated reactive and predictive approach to cloud elasticity. *Proc. Fourth Int. Conf. Cloud Computing, GRIDs, and Virtualization (CLOUD COMPUTING)*, Valencia, Spain, May 27–June 1, pp. 87–92. IARIA.
- [48] Casalicchio, E. and Perciballi, V. (2017) Auto-Scaling of Containers: The Impact of Relative and Absolute Metrics. *Proc. 2017 IEEE 2nd International Workshops on Foundations and Applications of Self* Systems (FAS*W)*, Tucson, USA, September 18–22, pp. 207–214. IEEE.
- [49] Al-Dhuraibi, Y., Paraiso, F., Djarallah, N. and Merle, P. (2017) Autonomic Vertical Elasticity of Docker Containers with ELASTICDOCKER. *Proc. 10th IEEE Int. Conf. Cloud Computing*, Honolulu, CA, June 25–30, pp. 1–9. IEEE.
- [50] Farokhi, S., Jamshidi, P., Lakew, E.B., Brandic, I. and Elmroth, E. (2016) A hybrid cloud controller for vertical memory elasticity: a control-theoretic approach. *Future Gener. Comput. Syst.*, **65**, 57–72.
- [51] Stankovski, V., Trmkoczy, J., Taherizadeh, S. and Cigale, M. (2016) Implementing time-critical functionalities with a distributed adaptive container architecture. *Proc. 18th Int. Conf. Information Integration and Web-based Applications and Services (iiWAS2016)*, Singapore, Singapore, November 28–30, pp. 455–459. ACM.
- [52] Hoenisch, P., Weber, I., Schulte, S., Zhu, L. and Fekete, A. (2015) Four-fold auto-scaling on a contemporary deployment platform using docker containers. *Proc. Int. Conf. Service-Oriented Computing*, Goa, India, November 16–19, pp. 316–323. Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- [53] Piraghaj, S.F., Calheiros, R.N., Chan, J., Dastjerdi, A.V. and Buyya, R. (2015) Virtual machine customization and task mapping architecture for efficient allocation of cloud data center resources. *Comp. J.*, **59**, 208–224.